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(Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and ... Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. 2025)

Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and High-Tech Assistive Technology in Special Education Schools in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed availability, adequacy and use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technologies in special education schools in North West Nigeria. The study used descriptive survey method to sought data from 120 teachers who were drawn using simple random sampling technique from teachers of students with physical disabilities. Two research questions were raised to guide the study. Researchers designed questionnaire and observation checklist were used to collect data. The two instruments were subjected to expert assessment for face and content validity check. The reliability of the instruments was established through pilot study using 20 teachers from two special needs schools within the study area, but not part of the sampled schools. The reliability values of 0.80 and 0.74 were obtained for the questionnaire and Checklist using Cronbach Alpha formula and Cohen's Kappa inter-rater reliability formula. The data collected were analyzed using percentage, mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technologies were not adequately available in special education schools. The few available Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices were not adequate. However, special education teachers do not use the available Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices to teach students with physical disabilities. It was recommended among other things that both the federal and state governments should improve on funding special education so as to ensure that the necessary Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices are made available in special education schools.

Key Words: *Availability, Adequacy, Utilization, Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory, High-tech, Assistive Technology, Special Education*

Introduction

Education is accepted globally as the cornerstone for the advancement of individuals and for national development. For this reasons Nigeria as a nation has emphasized in its National Policy on Education that every child irrespective of location, social, economic or physical characteristics must receive basic education (FRN, 2004). In order to provide efficient and productive education for the citizens, especially in this era of technological advancement, education in all regards need to be integrated with technology that can improve performance capabilities, encourage students' participation in instructional activities and facilitate their overall academic achievement. Thus, technology integration in education

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encompasses hardware and software applications deeply rooted in Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

Information and Communication Technology cut across wide range of computerized and electronic technologies used in the acquisition, processing, transmission, and storage of information (Adebisi, 2014). Advancement in ICT, its acceptance and use in education is indeed promising. Increasing involvement of ICT in education is bringing changes to the way teachers teach and learners learn. Information and Communication-based Technology is facilitating the growth of special education technology in Nigeria (Felicia, Sharif, Wong & Marriappan, 2014). Implementation of new teaching and learning tools, especially within the scope of special education is a blessing at the right time. Hence, the use of appropriate technological tools, devices, equipment, and gadgets in the classroom is significant to facilitating effective teaching and learning, which in turn will enhance positive performance and achievement of both instructors and learners. Thus, teacher's ability to integrate technology, pedagogy, and content in his/her classroom is paramount to a successful teaching and learning process.

The term Special education according to the National Policy on Education (2004) is "a customized education programme, designed to meet the unique needs of persons with special needs that the general education programme cannot provide". As a means for meeting special education needs, it is concerned with the elimination of barriers to educational participation. This involves setting the right place with appropriate technologies. Because of the support technologies offered to individuals with disabilities, they are addressed as assistive technology.

In recent years, the concept of assistive technology has emerged to dominate the field of special education. Assistive Technology encompasses any item, piece of equipment or system that helps a child with disability bypass, work around or compensate for the areas of difficulties (Raskind, 2009). Assistive technologies differ widely in quality and effectiveness. Today, different assistive technologies (low-tech, mid-tech and high-tech) are used to provide individuals with disabilities with educational opportunities, bringing out the cognitive potential in them, while enabling the curricula and teachers to achieve their objectives and enable the students with disabilities to participate in the learning process.

Students with disabilities connotes persons who have long-time physical, mental, emotional, or sensory impairments, whose interaction with the different attitudinal and environmental barriers prevent them from full and or effective performance within the classroom on an equal basis with others (Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2016). Students with physical disabilities are just a segment of students with disabilities. Students with physical disabilities are faced with abnormality or loss of function of physical structure. Thus, physical disability whether partial or total loss of ability, reduces the ability of the students to

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learn freely. Visual impairment, speech impairment, hearing impairment, and mobility limitation are the most common physical challenges found in special needs schools in Nigeria (Adebisi, 2014) United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund and World Health Organization joint report (UNICEF &WHO, 2015) acclaimed the need for the implementation of technology to support them in their functional deficits and to assist them access instruction and thus learn better.

In Nigeria, the provision of assistive technology in special education is significantly left in the hand of the government. Consequently, upon this, schools in Nigeria experienced infrastructural decay which has reduced their use in the classroom setting (Shikden, 2015). Notwithstanding this, it is important to note that the use of assistive technologies to facilitate teaching and learning activities within the special education ecosystem cannot be over emphasized. This is because they are considered as students allies capable of enhancing functional capabilities and encouraging their participation in education. Assistive technology helps students with special needs to improve their academic achievement. Nevertheless, not all assistive technologies can offer help to all students with special needs at all time. As students with physical disabilities progresses in learning, their technological needs also increase (Coleman, 2011). Researchers noticed that with the current technological development, traditional assistive technologies are becoming more of crutch than support tools (Rowlands, 2015). Thus, integrating emerging technologies into special education programmes will not only offer help but increase the opportunities of students with disabilities to meeting their educational aspirations. Because of its potential in improving the living and learning condition of Individuals with disabilities high-tech assistive technology is becoming popular among families of people with disabilities and professional (Adedapo, Nwosu, & Ibitoye, 2009). Hence, for the purpose of facilitating academic achievement of students with physical disabilities in the 21st century, effective and efficient mobilization and utilization 21st century assistive technologies should not be compromised.

Although, there is a gradual involvement, acceptance and utilization of new innovation in Nigeria; it is a mistake to think narrowly about assistive technology in this country (Oyundoyin, 2013). The entire assistive technology spectrum could be obtainable and holds promise for individuals with disabilities in Nigeria. Even though, there is no records indicating the widespread use of emerging phenomenon (high tech assistive technologies) in Nigeria, but index available shows that computers are available for classroom use in special schools. Findings from earlier researches show that students with disabilities use computers as often as their abled peers from the conventional schools. Although computers are the technology most often associated with high tech, there could be many other potentially valuable devices available in Nigeria. Considering its educational significance, it is therefore important that availability, adequacy and utilization of high-tech AT should be the central focus of stakeholders concerned with development of special education programme

(Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and ... Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. 2025)
in Nigeria.

More so, as an emerging technology, there are still a little quantitative evaluation of their availability, adequacy, use and performance (Wosu, Charles, & Samuel, 2016). Additionally, very little is known about special education teachers' use of high-tech AT to perform teaching tasks in the special school in Nigeria. Therefore, there is the need to conduct investigative research so as to assess the level of availability, adequacy and utilization of high technologies currently in special education programmes for the physically challenged students in special needs schools in North West Nigeria.

Furthermore, the rate of development of any nation lies on the quality of its science and technology products and delivery at all levels, which further translates the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of Nigeria as a nation aspiring to be developed and great at the global scale (Paul, 2022 & Peter, 2021), this further emphasizes the need to pay adequate attention to science education programs at all levels. Thus, an effective teaching and learning of sciences can only be meaningful and interesting when there is a conducive learning environment, which among other factors is addressing security challenges in the face of banditry activities which have ravaged most communities, shot down schools and rendered most people homeless (Sunday, 2022).

The current state of Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) programs especially in government secondary schools today, appears to be of great concern to science education stake holders, especially in Zamfara State, known to be educationally disadvantaged when compared with other states within the North west geopolitical zones of Nigeria, such as Kaduna, Katsina, Sokoto and Kebbi States, respectively. Several findings have revealed that integration of STEM program for teaching and learning of science subjects among Secondary Schools in North-west, Nigeria are not adequately implemented (Musa, 2022., Alebiosu, 2020., Muhammad, 2019 & Dike, 2015). This may be attributed to either security challenges, inadequate technological know-how and material resource management. However, this has contributed to students' poor academic performance in science related subjects (Ihejiamazu, 2021., Ayeni, 2020 & Owoeye, 2011).

The National Examination Council (NECO) and West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners reports on senior secondary students' academic performance in science subjects independently revealed poor results in general Sciences and Science Subject results were not encouraging (NECO & WAEC, 2020-2023). This may be due to poor acquisition of science process skills by students (Ojonugwa, 2019), Lack of adequate awareness on new innovation strategy and practical skills by science teachers and lack of well-equipped science laboratory in most government secondary schools (Okudili, 2018). In many schools in Nigeria, teachers and students are struggling to teach and learn with inadequate and or obsolete laboratory facilities

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(Sunday, 2022., Peter, 2021 & Dike, 2015). The current trend creates a wide gap with the tenets of education in Nigeria which stipulates that education should aim at helping the child acquire appropriate process and product skills, not to only excel in school but to live and contribute to the development of his society by addressing the basic needs of his immediate community and the nation at large (Edoga, 2021 & Akomolafe, 2015).

Effective implementation of STEM Education program through availability of instructional facilities in a well secured and academically conducive environment could be an alternative means of intervention by providing access to laboratory facilities and activities for science teaching and learning among secondary school students in Zamfara state and possibly Nigeria at large. When laboratory facilities of this nature are provided, it will help science students to develop problem-solving skills (Fatokun & Omenesa, 2019), promote critical thinking skills (Bichi, 2020 & Bolaji, 2019), acquire scientific and technological literacy that are 21st century learning skills base on world best practices (Fataba, 2019). Therefore, it is pertinent to note that provision of necessary intervention of this nature to students broadens their background in the area of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education propagation and product delivery to the society (Sunday, 2022 & Edoga, 2021). On the basis of this background, this proposed research study intends to investigate availability, adequacy and use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technologies in special education schools in North West Nigeria.

Research Problem

Ideally, Science, Technology, Engineering and mathematics (STEM) Education Programs are influenced when skills are acquired as learning outcome (Paul & Sunday, 2022, Okudili, 2018), But the situation currently have been a major cause of concern to science education stakeholders. Thus, Lack of adequate instructional facilities, Human resource management and incessant attack on students and schools have been identified as factors responsible for lack of adequate skills acquisition among secondary school students in Nigeria (Sunaday, 2022 & Bichi, 2020). and Lack of adequate awareness on modern innovative strategies, especially in most remote secondary schools in Northwest, Nigeria. Furthermore, there has been a major cause of mass failure in science related subjects over some few years ago among senior secondary school students Northwest, Nigeria (NECO & WAEC, 2020-2023). Invariably, this lingering problem has prevented the state from producing required number of qualified Scientists, Technologists, Engineers, Health workers, among others. However, graduates from such system Variably will lack the required knowledge and skills for 21st century to compete with their counterparts in other institutions of higher learning, based on global best practices.

Furthermore, since the inception of 21st century, individuals increasingly became immersed of technological changes and innovation; yet the situation in classrooms has not change.

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The problem of students domantness fed by a static pedagogical method is as old as the classroom itself.

However, the emphasis of today's education is student-centred learning which aimed at developing today's learner with problem solving skills, critical thinking ability and other skills necessary for survival beyond the four walls of the classroom. How learners access curriculum is crucial for the attainment of these current educational demands. For students with physical disabilities, access to the curriculum will require the use of assistive technologies. Assistive technology's Success is best evaluated by how it enables an individual with a disability to exercise self-determination and greater independence. The technology we used in education in the past lacked the necessary accessibility features available to guarantee the 21st century survival skills amidst the strong competition from able bodies. Research findings shows that despite the adoption of traditional technologies, still many of the students with disabilities in developing countries like Nigeria were experiencing barriers to their learning. These include difficulties in reading, writing and reception of information. Physically challenged students continue to learn under frustrating conditions. This causes drop out of many physically challenged students from school for street begging. Furthermore, the very few who manage to graduate from school certainly do so without necessary skills for survival and as such they found it difficult to be absorbed by today's labour market. Additionally, the few that were lucky to be employed on condition of their status find it difficult to perform on the job because they weren't adequately trained using today's technologies. Therefore, providing low technologies is not enough to meeting the needs of people with disabilities effectively. High-Tech assistive options were developed to offer the best way of assist to individuals with disabilities to succeed in the classroom, community, and workplace.

Research in the area of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and or high-tech assistive technology availability and use is relatively narrow due to it being a relatively new phenomenon in education, the scaring price tag of some of these life-changing devices as well as slow nature of developing countries like Nigeria to accepting new innovation. In essence, there are no home-based studies that see the development and use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technology for teaching and learning of students in special schools, even though, some were reported to existed. It is this gap in research and development that prompt the desire from the researchers to undertake research on the availability, adequacy and use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technology in special needs schools in North West Nigeria.

Research Questions

(Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and ... Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. 2025)

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

- i. How often do teachers make use of the available Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technology for the teaching of physically challenged students in special education schools in North West Nigeria?
- ii. What are the major factors that are preventing teachers from effective utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices in teaching the physically challenged students in special education schools in North West Nigeria?

Research Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey research method because the designed made it possible for the researchers to have a broad view from a sample of special education teachers in the special education schools in order to draw conclusions regarding availability, adequacy and utilization of high-tech assistive technology.

The population for this study include all teachers of special education schools in North West Nigeria. There are 354 special education teachers spread across seven public special education schools in North West Nigeria. The target population for this study comprised of special education teachers from the comprehensive special education schools in North West Nigeria. One hundred and twenty (120) special education teachers were sampled from the population through simple random sampling technique from three comprehensive special education schools. The three selected special education schools were Kaduna State Special Education School, Kaduna, Kebbi State Special Needs School, Birnin-kebbi and Special Education School, Tudun Maliki Kano.

Two different instruments were used to collect the required information for the study. The two instruments used were questionnaire and observation checklist. The questionnaire titled "Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and Teachers High-Tech Assistive Technology Utilization Questionnaire (MMLTHATUQ)". The questionnaire has two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A sought information in line with the respondents' personal data, including information regarding teaching domain and gender among others. On the other hand, section B sought relevant information needed to address the problem under study. It is structured in Likert Scale pattern with options of Frequently (F) = 5 points, Sometimes (S) = 4, Rarely (R) = 3, Once (O) = 2, and Not at all (N) = 1, respectively. The checklist titled: "Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and High-Tech Assistive Technology Availability in Special Education Schools (MMLHATASES)". The checklist included a list of some of high-tech assistive devices/software needed for the education of individuals with physical disabilities. MMLHATASES has provision for name of school as well as location of the school. Additionally, it has provision for the researcher to assess adequacy of these technologies. The checklist is divided into five sections: Section A, B, C, D & E which consisted of Multi-

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Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices/software for visual impairments, hearing impairments, speech impairments, motor impairments, and multiple impairments, respectively.

The instruments were subjected to expert assessment in order to determine their face and content validity. Three lecturers from the Department of Educational Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna, and two special education experts from Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau assessed the comprehensiveness, adequacy and clarity of the items. Corrections and suggestions raised by these experts were effected accordingly in the final drafted questionnaires. The reliability of the instruments used were established through pilot testing with 20 teachers from two special needs schools within the study area, but not part of the sampled schools. The reliability value of 0.81 was obtained for the questionnaire using Cronbach Alpha formula and 0.74 was obtained for the checklist using Cohen’s Kappa’s inter- rater reliability formula. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics such as percentage, mean and standard deviation.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Respondents According to Teaching Areas

Teaching Area	KSSSES		KSSNS		SESK	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Teachers of Visually Impaired Students (VI)	15	37.5	10	25	12	30
Teachers of Hearing-Impaired Students (HI)	16	40	13	32.5	10	25
Teachers of Speech Impaired Students (SI)	-	-	4	10	5	12.5
Teachers of Students with Motor Limitation (ML)	-	-	6	15	5	12.5
Teachers of Students with Multiple Impairment (MPI)	9	22.5	7	17.5	8	20
Total	40	100	40	100	40	100

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents according to teaching domains in the three sampled schools. It shows that, out of 40 respondents in Kaduna State Special Education School, 15 (37.5%) are VI teachers, 16 (40%) are HI teachers and 9 (22.5%) are MPI teachers; Kebbi State Special Needs School (KSSNS) has 10 (25%) VI teachers, 13 (32.5%) HI teachers, 4 (10%) SI teachers, 6 (15%) MI teachers and 7 (17.5%) MPI teachers; while Special education School, Tudun Maliki, Kano has 12 (30%) VI teachers, 10 (25%) HI teachers, 5 (12.5%) SI teachers, 5 (12.5%) ML teachers and 8 (20%) MPI teachers. Cumulatively, there are 37 (30.8%) VI teachers, 39 (32.5%) HI teachers, 9 (7.5%) SI teachers, 11 (9.2%) ML teachers and 24 (20%) MPI teachers, respectively.

Research Question 1: How often do you use Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and

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assistive device(s) or software when teaching physically challenged students in your school?

The extent to which special education teachers make use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices and software in teaching students with physical disabilities was analysed based on their utilization of assistive devices/software on the domains of frequently, sometimes, rarely, once, or not at all. The mean and standard deviation of their responses was calculated and shown in table 1 below.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and High-Tech Assistive Devices and Software by Special Education Teachers

SN	Items	School	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
I	I use high-tech assistive device(s) / software to facilitate teaching and learning in the classroom.	KSSES	40	2.3	1.11	Not At All
		KSSNS	40	2.9	1.49	Not At All
		SESK	40	2.9	1.45	Not At All
II	I use high-tech assistive device(s) / software to actively engage the physically challenged students in the classroom.	KSSES	40	2.7	1.32	Not At All
		KSSNS	40	2.3	1.31	Not At All
		SESK	40	2.6	1.63	Not At All
III	I use high-tech assistive device(s) / software to assess the physically challenged students in the classroom.	KSSES	40	2.6	1.48	Not At All
		KSSNS	40	2.8	1.50	Not At All
		SESK	40	2.9	1.42	Not At All
IV	I use high-tech assistive device(s) / software to generate teaching aids for classroom presentation.	KSSES	40	2.7	1.28	Not At All
		KSSNS	40	2.1	1.18	Not At All
		SESK	40	2.7	1.20	Not At All
V	I use high-tech assistive device(s) / software to enhance physically challenged students' participation in the classroom.	KSSES	40	2.4	1.22	Not At All
		KSSNS	40	2.5	1.57	Not At All
		SESK	40	2.6	1.53	Not At All
Grand Mean				2.6	Not At All	
Decision Mean =3.0						

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation analysis on the extent of special education teachers' use of assistive devices in special education schools. Specifically, item one which states that "I ... use assistive devices to facilitate teaching and learning in the classroom" has mean scores of 2.3, 2.9 and 2.9 with standard deviation of 1.11, 1.49, and 1.45, respectively. Similarly, item 2 which states that "I ... use assistive devices to actively engage students with physical disabilities in the classroom" has mean scores of 2.7, 2.3 and 2.6 with standard deviation of 1.32, 1.31 and 1.63, respectively. Item three which states that "I ... use assistive devices to assess students with physical disabilities in the classroom" has mean scores of 2.6, 2.8 and 2.9 with standard deviation of 1.48, 1.50

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and 1.42, respectively. Also, item four which states that “I ... use assistive devices to generate teaching aids for classroom presentation” has mean scores of 2.7, 2.1 and 2.7 with standard deviation of 1.28, 1.18 and 1.20, respectively. Furthermore, item five which states that “I ... use high-tech assistive devices to enhance students with physical disabilities participation in the classroom” has mean scores of 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6 with the standard deviation of 1.22, 1.57 and 1.53, respectively. On a general note, it can be deduced from the results presented in Table 2 that teachers do not make use of high- tech assistive devices and software in teaching students with physical disabilities in special education schools. This is because all the items that measure teachers’ level of utilization of assistive devices had mean scores that were below the decision mean score of 3.0.

Research Question 2: What are the factors that prevent you from effective utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high- tech assistive devices in teaching the physically challenged students in special needs schools in North West Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on Factors Preventing Special Education Teachers from making Effective Use of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and High-Tech Assistive Devices and Software in Teaching the Physically Challenged Students

SN	Items	School	N	X	SD	Decision
I	Inadequacy of assistive devices and software limits their use in the classroom	KSSES	40	3.6	1.19	Agree
		KSSNS	40	3.4	1.37	Agree
		SESK	40	3.4	1.43	Agree
II	Inadequate electricity supply reduces the use of assistive devices and software in the classroom	KSSES	40	3.6	1.24	Agree
		KSSNS	40	3.7	1.32	Agree
		SESK	40	3.3	1.40	Agree
III	Poor classroom setting hinders the use of assistive devices in the classroom	KSSES	40	3.5	1.24	Agree
		KSSNS	40	3.4	1.56	Agree
		SESK	40	3.9	1.08	Agree
IV	Lack of awareness on the existence of assistive devices in schools hinders their Use	KSSES	40	3.8	1.34	Agree
		KSSNS	40	4.1	0.92	Agree
		SESK	40	3.9	1.05	Agree
V	Lack of training reduces the use of assistive devices/software in the classroom	KSSES	40	3.5	1.28	Agree
		KSSNS	40	3.7	1.33	Agree
		SESK	40	3.8	1.17	Agree
Grand Mean				3.6		Agree

Decision Mean = 3.0

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of special education teachers’ response on the

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factors that hinders their effective use of assistive devices in the classroom. The analysis of the table reveals the mean scores of 3.6, 3.4 and 3.4 with standard deviation of 1.19, 1.37 and 1.43, respectively for item one which states that “inadequacy of assistive devices limits their use in the classroom”. Also, item two which states that “inadequate electricity supply reduces the use of assistive devices in the classroom” has mean scores of 3.6, 3.7 and 3.3 with standard deviation of 1.24, 1.32 and 1.40, respectively. Item three which states that “poor classroom setting hinders the use of assistive devices in the classroom has mean scores of 3.5, 3.4 and 3.9 and standard deviation of 1.24, 1.56 and 1.08, respectively. In the same manner, item four which states that “lack of awareness on the existence of assistive devices hinders their use in the classroom” has mean scores of 3.8, 4.1 and 3.9 with standard deviation of 1.34, 0.92, and 1.05, respectively. Furthermore, item five which states that “lack of training reduces the use of assistive devices in the classroom” has mean scores of 3.5, 3.7 and 3.8 with standard deviation of 1.28, 1.33 and 1.17, respectively. Generally, the table reveals the grand mean score of 3.6 which is greater than the decision mean score of 3.0. This implies to a greater extent that the presented significantly hindered special education teachers from effective use of assistive devices in the classroom.

Summary of Major Findings

The summary of major findings from this study includes:

- (i) Special education teachers do not effectively use Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory/assistive devices and software in teaching students with physical disabilities in the selected special education schools.
- (ii) Factors such as inadequacy of assistive devices, inadequate power supply, classroom setting, lack of training and lack of knowledge on the present of these assistive devices in schools hindered their utilization in special education schools.

Discussion of Findings

This aim of this research is to assess availability, determine adequacy and extent to which special education teachers use high-tech assistive devices and software in teaching students with physical disabilities in special education schools in North West Nigeria. In line with research question one and two, the assessment on the extent at which special education teachers used assistive devices available in their school was based on five different items. Unfortunately, most special education teachers do not use assistive devices and software at all in teaching students with physical disabilities. This may be due to teachers’ lack of awareness of the existence of such devices in their respective schools, and perhaps because of the inadequacy of the device. This finding corroborates with the finding of Maraizu (2014) which maintained that most of special education coordinator surveyed in Enugu state, Nigerian reported that teachers do not use technology to teach because of the insufficient supply of such devices in special education schools. This is indeed alarming considering the significance of technology to special need students learning. However, the

(Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and ... Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. 2025)

finding of this study is not in agreement with finding of Shikden (2015) which concluded that special education teachers used assistive devices regularly in the classroom. On the contrary, this finding agreed with the finding of Onivehu, Ohawuiro, and Oyeniran (2017) which discovered that teachers of students with physical disabilities were not using assistive devices to teach because of their high-tech nature and because they were not adequately available and accessible by teachers.

Another finding that aroused from this study also revealed some major factors that hindered the special education teachers in North West geopolitical zone of Nigeria from effectively using assistive devices available in their respective schools in classroom presentation. The finding revealed problems that include inadequacy of assistive devices, inadequate power supply, poor classroom setting, lack of training and lack of awareness on the present of these assistive devices in schools as major barriers to the effective use of assistive devices by teachers in special education school within the geopolitical zone under study. This finding corroborates with the finding of Coleman (2011) which discovered unused assistive devices sitting on shelves and stored in schools stores while teachers were not aware of their existence in the school. Similarly, the finding agreed with the finding of Shikden (2015) which found out that teachers lack of competency in assistive technology, insufficiency of assistive technologies and lack of regular electricity supply were among the major factors that hindered the effective use of assistive devices in special education schools in North Central Nigeria. The finding is also in line with the finding of AJuwon and Chitiyo (2015) which discovered that lack of training in the use of assistive devices, lack of appropriate assistive devices and services in the classroom and irregular electricity supply as the biggest challenges regarding assistive technology utilization in special education schools in Nigeria. The similarities of these findings may be attributed to the fact that the studies focused on the use of assistive devices by special education teachers who were expected to use assistive technology to facilitate teaching and learning of students with disabilities in special education schools.

Implications of Findings

Based on the findings of this study, the following implications were drawn.

The integration of emerging technologies in teaching and learning has become a global trend. Hence, no country would like to be left out this development because of the enormous benefits attached to it. Consequently, upon this, finding of this study shows that most high-tech assistive technologies required for the teaching and learning of students with special needs were not adequately available in special education schools. The implication of this finding is that special education teachers would not be able to effectively integrate these forms of innovation in the teaching and learning process in order to enhance quality special education.

Integration of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technologies in teaching and learning of special education students will help to improve the quality of

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(Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and ... Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. 2025)

special education. High-tech assistive devices provide students with special needs the opportunity to acquire necessary skills for 21st century survival. However, it is disheartening to note that majority of special education teachers do not make use of the available Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices/ software in the classroom. This implies that teachers lack the skills to implement new innovations in special education. Therefore, even when government and other stakeholders provide Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technologies for special education, the hope of quality special education may not be attained because special education teachers do not make use of innovative pedagogies regularly to implement curriculum.

The application of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive technologies is paramount to providing quality special education. Unfortunately, certain factors such as poor electricity supply, traditional classroom setting, lack of training and inadequacy of these technologies among others pauses barriers which prevent it from becoming a reality. By implication, quality special education in Nigeria can only be achieved when such barriers identified by teachers are adequately addressed.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the analysis of the data collected for this study, the researchers conclude that Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices/ software that are required for the effective teaching and learning of students with physical disabilities in special education schools across North West Nigeria were not largely available. Only few assistive devices and software were found available in special education schools, however they were not adequate. This inadequacy of assistive devices necessary for teaching and learning of students with special needs can be attributes to poor funding of special education and lack of regular supply of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive technology by the government. The study also concluded that the few Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices available in special education schools were found not in good condition. The poor state of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive technology in special education schools can be attributed to fact that some of these devices and software are over stretched and some might have faced the taste of time and because they are not properly kept, they developed faults and malfunction.

In terms of use, the study discovered that special education teachers do not use Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices available in teaching students with physical disabilities in special education schools. The unused can be attributed to inadequacy of the available Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices/ software, lack of awareness on the existing Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices in schools, irregular power supply and inability to operate Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and high-tech assistive devices.

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(Availability, Adequacy and Utilization of Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and ... Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. 2025)

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were given.

- (i) Both the federal and state governments should improve on funding special education technologies so as to ensure that the necessary Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices are made available in a required quantity in special education schools.
- (ii) Government and other stakeholders should organize workshop, seminars and other capacity building training regularly for teachers as means of updating their knowledge and skills in the use of emerging Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive devices considering the dynamic nature of special education technology.
- (iii) Government, school administrators and other stakeholders in special education should work towards improving power supply, upgrading classrooms to a standard that will guarantee Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive technology utilization and creating awareness regarding Multi-Functional Mobile Laboratory and assistive technologies available in special education schools. This will help to curb the problem of abandonment and underuse of assistive technologies in special education schools.

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